

Marketing Aspects of Gastronomic Tourism Development in Georgia

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ABSTRACT

The article highlights that Georgia possesses valuable experience in tourism and has the resources necessary to develop various forms of it. The country's natural beauty, rich historical heritage, distinctive cuisine, and cultural traditions inherited from ancestors all create significant potential for tourism growth. In discussing gastronomic tourism and its prospects, the author emphasizes that the defining factor for its development in Georgia is the uniqueness of Georgian cuisine. The article notes that, unlike other types of tourism, gastronomic tourism can be cultivated in any country, which may explain its widespread popularity and rapid expansion. It is stressed that national dishes play a key role in shaping a country's identity. Georgia offers a wide variety of such dishes, further enriched by its vibrant table culture. Of particular importance is Georgia's status as the birthplace of wine. Wine, together with the tradition of hospitality and the diversity of Georgian dishes, forms a strong foundation for the identity of the Georgian table. These elements hold great potential to provide tourists with memorable experiences and emotional satisfaction, thereby opening broad opportunities for the growth of gastronomic tourism. The article underscores that success in this field depends on effective marketing. According to the author, the Georgian National Tourism Administration is taking gradual and appropriate steps in this direction. However, the absence of a unified strategy for gastronomic tourism means that marketing efforts may not always achieve the desired results. Therefore, the timely creation of a comprehensive strategy is essential. Such a strategy would enable Georgia to more actively leverage its national cuisine in shaping a positive image as a leading tourist destination.

KEYWORDS: Tourism, gastronomic tourism, Georgian cuisine

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INTRODUCTION

The tourism sector plays an increasingly important role in the global economy, a trend directly linked to the process of globalization. There are many factors that drive people's interest in the tourism industry. Among them, two stand out: the relatively small amount of capital required to start a tourism business compared to other economic sectors, and the ability to recover investments quickly. However, for a tourism business to succeed, a country must possess resources that can be transformed into tourism products appealing to both domestic and international travelers. It can be confidently stated that nearly every country has potential for tourism development, given the wide range of interests among travelers. Some are drawn to nature walks, others to cultural heritage, some to religious sites, while others seek adventure-filled experiences. Many travelers are eager to explore the food culture of different nations, taste local dishes, or immerse themselves in rural life. As a result, diverse forms of tourism have emerged and developed, including ecotourism, cultural tourism, pilgrimage tourism, adventure tourism, gastronomic tourism, wine tourism, agrotourism, etc.

People who love to travel can satisfy their interests in Georgia in many directions. This is made possible by the nature of Georgia, its historical past, cultural monuments, unique Georgian cuisine, the heritage left by ancestors in all spheres of life. We cannot fail to add to this the fact that in a country small in terms of territory and population, there is diverse nature and a mild climate. A person who loves to travel can travel to the mountains and visit the Black Sea in one day. Georgia is rich in lakes, rivers, waterfalls, which is very important for those who love hiking and fishing in nature. And, most importantly, tourists are met in the country by the hospitable Georgian people, who consider guests a gift from God. The tradition of hospitality among the Georgian

people, and in the entire Caucasus in general, has been formed over the centuries and is still preserved today. In addition, there are regions in Georgia in which ancient Georgian traditions have been preserved, one might say, unchanged, which leaves tourists satisfied and, most likely, will be so in the future.

Tourism is not a new area of activity for Georgia. Foreign visitors have been traveling to the country since ancient times, and many continued to do so even during the Soviet era (Seturi, M. 2018). As a result, Georgia has accumulated valuable experience in the tourism sector, providing a strong foundation for future success. This potential is further reflected in the country's recent developments in this field.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the course of working on this topic, we first examined a wide range of literary sources on tourism in general, and gastronomic tourism in particular. We reviewed the works of numerous Georgian and foreign scholars and researchers [Todua, N. (2017, 2019, 2021); Seturi, M. (2018, 2019, 2025); Khokhobaia, M. (2018, 2019, 2021); Roblek, V., Petrovic, N., Gagnidze, I., Khokhobaia, M. (2021); Liutikac, D. (2023); Ola Bazaza (2019); Tannia Elizabeth Huertas Lopez, Yenis Cuetara Hernandez, Leonardo Manuel Cuerara Sanchez, Milton Marino Villarreal Pastaz (2019); Gheorghe, G., Tudorache, P., Nistoreanu, P. (2014); Boyko, V., Horozhankina, N., Korneyev, M., Shcholokova, H., Umanska, S. (2024), among others]. These works provided the theoretical and methodological foundation for this article. Alongside the study of academic literature, we also examined relevant legal documents. In particular, we analyzed the tourism subsection of the Government Program of Georgia for 2025–2028 (7, pp. 28–29), which outlines the tasks planned for the coming years to ensure the continued development of tourism. We reviewed the Georgian Law on Tourism, as well as statistical data from the yearbooks of 2024 and 2025 published by the National Statistics Service of Georgia, focusing on the tourism sector and the provision of tourist accommodation facilities. Additionally, we studied reports prepared in recent years by the Research and Planning Department of the National Tourism Administration of Georgia, along with other materials available on its official website and information on ongoing projects. In preparing this article, we employed both general and statistical research methods. The materials obtained from different sources were analyzed in logical connection with one another, and our conclusions were formed through comparison of the results.

THE ROLE OF TOURISM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GEORGIAN ECONOMY

Tourism plays a significant role in Georgia's economy. It is among the fastest-growing industries in the country (Todua, N., 2019) and, in recent years, has demonstrated steady global expansion according to various macroeconomic indicators (Khokhobaia, M., 2018).

The importance of tourism in Georgia continues to rise, as it generates profits more rapidly than many other economic sectors (Mghebrishvili, B., 2010). The tourism industry develops in close connection with other branches of the economy, with each sector mutually supporting the other in their activities (Gheorghe, G., Tudorache, P., Nistoreanu, P. (2014). As a result, the overall economy grows, and the standard of living gradually improves. Retail trade, in particular, benefits from this growth. The increasing number of visitors to the country positively influences retail development, expanding its opportunities (Mghebrishvili, B., 2019). This impact is especially evident when travelers come with the specific purpose of shopping.

The impact of tourism on Georgia's economy is most evident in its ability to create new jobs, thereby contributing to poverty reduction. The growth of tourism necessitates an expansion in accommodation facilities, which in turn generates additional employment opportunities. Recognizing this, the 2025–2028 government program placed strong emphasis on expanding the hotel network. The plan envisions the opening of more than 310 new tourist accommodation facilities, raising the total number of hotels to 2,680. As a result, both employment in the sector and household incomes are expected to rise. By 2019, prior to the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, 20,575 people were employed in Georgian hotels. In 2020, this number fell to 13,615 (22, p. 221). However, by 2024, thanks to state policies supporting tourism, employment in the sector had increased to 29,082 (23, p. 221) – a development that merits positive recognition. An increase in employment across any sector strengthens the population's purchasing power and, in turn, fosters broader economic growth.

With the rise in tourist numbers, the income of accommodation facilities also increases, becoming an important source of state budget revenue. In 2019, revenues from accommodation services amounted to 659.8 million GEL at current prices (22, p. 220). During the pandemic, this figure dropped sharply to 228.7 million GEL in 2020. In the following years, however, revenues gradually recovered, reaching 1,104.2 million GEL by 2024 (23, p. 220).

A notable strength of the tourism sector is its ability to generate employment opportunities for women (Ola Bazaza, 2019), thereby contributing to gender balance. By enabling women to showcase their entrepreneurial skills, tourism empowers them and enhances their role in the country's sustainable development.

Tourism growth also requires a strong infrastructure base (Seturi, M., 2025). As such, the sector directly influences improvements in roads, airports, transport, communications, and other facilities. Tourism thus acts as a driving force for the development of multiple economic sectors. Recognizing this, the Government of Georgia's 2025–2028 program includes plans to

invest more than 1 billion GEL in infrastructure upgrades over the next four years. These investments are expected to positively impact the quality of life for both citizens and visitors.

The tourism sector in Georgia continues to recover from the challenges brought about by the pandemic. The severe impact of COVID-19 on the industry is evident in the data provided by the National Statistics Service of Georgia. Nevertheless, thanks to marketing initiatives undertaken by the National Tourism Administration, the situation has improved considerably. By 2024, the total number of international visits reached 7,368,149, of which 5,091,732 were tourist visits. Revenue from international travel amounted to 4,425,376,937 USD (5). These figures demonstrate that Georgia is gradually overcoming the difficulties created by the pandemic and moving forward in the tourism sector.

The majority of international tourist visits to Georgia come from neighboring countries, though Israel also represents a significant source of visitors (24, p.10; 25, p.8). Tourists from European countries tend to originate mainly from former Soviet and socialist states, reflecting Georgia's recognition and cultural ties within these regions. The high number of visitors from Israel is largely explained by the presence of Georgian and former Soviet Jewish communities living there, who are familiar with Georgia's natural and cultural heritage and eager to reconnect with it. Compared to 2019 (pre-pandemic), only minor changes occurred in the top ten countries of origin for tourists to Georgia in 2024: Germany and Poland were replaced by Belarus and India. Although China, Saudi Arabia, and Uzbekistan did not rank among the top ten, the growth in tourist arrivals from these countries – particularly China – was substantial. Statistical data thus highlights a shifting geography of inbound tourism, with Asia emerging as an increasingly important source of visitors. To sustain this momentum, it is essential to strengthen Georgia's visibility as a favorable travel destination in European markets through targeted marketing campaigns. In this regard, the National Tourism Administration undertook significant initiatives in 2025, which are expected to yield positive results for the country in the near future.

We should focus on one key challenge in the further development of the tourism sector: establishing Georgia's image as a tourist destination. This goal is directly linked to the effective and targeted use of destination marketing tools (Todua, N., 2019; Mghebrishvili, B., 2013). Georgia can be considered a new player on the global tourism map, and novelty itself attracts visitors. Therefore, the country must be prepared to spark interest among more travelers and to provide them with high-quality services. To achieve this, it is essential to strengthen the competitiveness of the tourism product and enhance the country's visual appeal – through improved roads, greenery, and cleanliness. Equally important are the conscientious implementation of business practices, alignment of price and quality, and the proper arrangement of accommodation, transportation, food services, and safety measures. Efforts in these areas have long been underway, and the ultimate outcome is a satisfied visitor (tourist or excursionist), which in turn positively shapes the country's image.

According to the Georgian National Tourism Administration's *Statistical Review of Tourism in Georgia, 2024*, international visitor satisfaction levels are notably high: 53.1% of visitors reported being very satisfied, while 40.5% were satisfied. Only a small fraction expressed dissatisfaction – 0.7% dissatisfied and 0.3% very dissatisfied (25, p.11). This strong satisfaction rate is highly beneficial for Georgia, and promoting these results internationally will further strengthen the country's tourism image.

The contribution of tourism to Georgia's economy is evident in its share of the gross domestic product (GDP). Prior to the pandemic, in 2019, tourism accounted for 8.4% of GDP (24, p.29). This share declined sharply in 2020, dropping to 5.9%. In the following years, however, it gradually recovered, reaching 7.3% in 2024 – matching the level recorded in 2017 (25, p.26). These figures highlight the growing resilience of Georgia's tourism sector and its significant role in driving economic development.

GASTRONOMIC TOURISM AND CONDITIONS FOR ITS DEVELOPMENT IN GEORGIA

In recent years, global interest in food and culinary culture has grown significantly, leading to the emergence and development of gastronomic tourism as a distinct branch of the industry. Tourists today are drawn not only to the flavors and qualities of dishes – a universal attraction – but also to the stories behind their origins, the art of preparation, the traditions of serving, the ingredients used, and the cultural events that enhance knowledge of cuisine. This broad spectrum of culinary curiosity has fueled the rapid growth of gastronomic tourism.

Moreover, destinations and tourism enterprises worldwide increasingly recognize the importance of gastronomy as a means of diversifying tourism offerings and stimulating local, regional, and national economic development (32, p. 5). This awareness has further accelerated the advancement of gastronomic tourism, positioning it as a vital component of the modern travel experience.

One of the defining features of gastronomic tourism, distinguishing it from other forms of tourism, is that every country possesses the conditions for its development. This is because the indigenous population of any nation is characterized by a unique food culture, which forms an essential part of its identity. Scholarly articles on gastronomic tourism often highlight the culinary potential of specific countries, emphasizing the availability of authentic products with diverse flavors (Tannia Elizabeth Huertas Lopez, Yenis Cuetara Hernandez, Leonardo Manuel Cuerara Sánchez, Milton Marino Villarreal Pastaz, 2019). Clearly, many nations can offer tourists distinctive tastes that set them apart from others. Georgia is one such country, notable for its unique dishes, the traditions surrounding their presentation, and its rich culture of hospitality. The Georgian table captivates visitors not only with its cuisine but also with the institution of hospitality itself. The role of the *Tamada* – the toastmaster at the Georgian feast – represents a centuries-old model of democratic governance, a tradition confirmed by archaeological findings (35). This heritage underscores

Georgia's strong potential for developing gastronomic tourism. It is also important to recognize that gastronomy accompanies all forms of tourism. Gastronomic tourism is inherently integrated into every type of travel, since all tourists require food. In this sense, every traveler can be considered a gastronomic tourist. While some may not actively seek gastronomic events or cultural experiences related to cuisine, they remain interested in food products, their flavors, and the ways in which they are served.

It must be emphasized that the development of gastronomic tourism yields highly positive results for countries. This is largely due to the many advantages associated with this type of tourism, including: income generation; the development of tourist infrastructure; preservation of cultural heritage; enhancement of regional knowledge about food; the creation of a positive national image and identity based on cuisine; and meaningful interaction with the local community (Liutikac, D., 2023).

In Georgia, as in many other countries, gastronomic tourism has become increasingly popular and is regarded as one of the most fashionable forms of tourism (Nakashidze R., Beridze R., Govorukha E., Evlash T., 2021). Its appeal can be explained by several factors: the enjoyment of leisure time; the opportunity to observe unique nutritional traditions of a particular country; the chance to experience diverse cuisines by appreciating the taste qualities of dishes, learning about their origins, understanding the culture of serving them, and witnessing their preparation. We share the view that gastronomic tourism is not merely a business – it is also an opportunity to discover new and interesting dishes, visit factories, wineries, and farms (Diasamidze, G., 2021), and gain satisfaction from these experiences. For those engaged in this field, a proper understanding of its essence ensures the success of their business.

In our view, gastronomic tourism can play a significant role in addressing regional challenges and, consequently, in fostering the development of the Georgian economy. Specifically, we refer to the difficulties faced by the Georgian countryside, including migration not only from rural areas to the capital but also abroad. Gastronomic tourism, together with wine and agrotourism, creates employment opportunities and generates income for the rural population. To some extent, it is precisely with the aim of tackling these rural issues that the Georgian National Tourism Administration has introduced projects such as *Wine Road* (34) and *Mziskari* (33). While the primary goal of both initiatives is to develop tourism products and increase visitor numbers, they also deliver substantial benefits to rural communities. Our particular focus here is the *Mziskari* project, launched in 2024. This initiative represents a nationwide network of family-based hospitality. It brings to life the cultural heritage of Georgian gastronomy and the traditions of dining and hospitality across different regions, offering tourists authentic experiences. Through *Mziskari*, visitors can discover new flavors, appreciate the value of Georgian hospitality, and immerse themselves in regional culinary traditions. We believe this project should be promoted more actively among both the local population and international tourists. The greater the participation of families, the stronger the impact of gastronomic tourism on rural communities and, ultimately, on the national economy.

Moreover, to attract gastronomic tourists to Georgia's regions, marketing efforts should highlight the unique culinary features specific to each area. By emphasizing these distinctive regional cuisines, promotional campaigns can significantly increase tourist interest in exploring the diverse gastronomic landscape of Georgia.

To promote the development of gastronomic tourism, various associations have been established in many countries. In Georgia, these include the Georgian Gastronomic Tourism Business Association, the Georgian Gastronomy Association, and the Georgian Restaurateurs Association, among others. Such organizations play an important role in helping the tourism sector address the challenges it faces in its operations.

Nevertheless, in our view, despite the diverse efforts undertaken by the Government of Georgia and the National Tourism Administration, the full potential of gastronomic tourism in the country remains underutilized. Current legislative documents related to tourism give insufficient attention to this sector. For instance, the *Georgian Tourism Strategy 2025* makes no reference to gastronomic tourism. We believe that wherever the traditions and history of winemaking are highlighted – particularly in connection with Georgia's status as the "homeland of wine" – Georgian cuisine should also be emphasized. Similarly, gastronomic tourism is absent from the Law on Tourism of Georgia. At present, Georgia lacks a unified marketing strategy for gastronomic tourism. Without such a framework, it is impossible to properly coordinate promotional activities, reflect regional interests, and implement a consistent nationwide policy. We are convinced that a unified strategy would enhance the international presentation of Georgian gastronomy, strengthen branding efforts, and ensure that achievements in this field are communicated effectively. In its absence, however, regions may disseminate contradictory information about the country's gastronomic experience, potentially undermining tourists' confidence. Furthermore, some traditional dishes risk remaining overlooked, and service quality across regions may vary significantly. We therefore believe that the absence of a unified marketing strategy for gastronomic tourism could lead to several undesirable consequences. It is essential that such a strategy be developed promptly, ensuring that Georgian gastronomy is properly promoted, coordinated, and positioned both domestically and internationally.

Georgia possesses significant potential for the development of gastronomic tourism. As previously noted, this potential is rooted in the country's unique and diverse cuisine, which serves as one of Georgia's main attractions (Diasamidze, G., 2021). The key lies in effectively utilizing this culinary heritage within tourism marketing. It is well established that shaping a positive image of a country through its national cuisine is a successful marketing strategy for attracting tourists (Boyko, V., Horozhankina, N., Korneyev, M., Shcholokova, H., Umanska, S., 2024). In our view, the Georgian Tourism Administration applies this approach, as

evidenced by the information on Georgian cuisine featured on its official tourism page. This page is available to potential visitors in both Georgian and English, ensuring accessibility to a wider audience. The effectiveness of this platform is reflected in statistical data showing steady growth in tourist numbers and high levels of visitor satisfaction. It can be argued that the AIDA model functions successfully within Georgia's tourism sector. The design of the tourism page captures the attention of potential visitors, stimulates their interest, awakens their desire to travel to Georgia, and ultimately motivates them to take action. The results are clear: the number of foreign tourists continues to increase annually. This demonstrates that the creators of the Georgian tourism page understand both what information to provide and how best to present it to potential tourists.

The Georgia tourism page highlights why travelers should choose Georgia as their destination. It introduces potential gastronomic tourists to the richness of Georgian cuisine, describing it as a true paradise for both vegetarians and vegans. While Georgia lies at the crossroads of Europe and Asia along the Silk Road – its culinary traditions influenced by neighboring cultures – its cuisine remains authentically Georgian. Many dishes, such as *satsivi*, *shkmeruli*, and *baje*, have entirely local origins. Altogether, the Georgia tourism page serves as a powerful marketing tool for attracting visitors.

EXTENSIVE CONCLUSION

The study of the marketing aspects of gastronomic tourism in Georgia demonstrates that the country possesses significant potential to secure its rightful place in the global tourism market. At the heart of this potential lies Georgia's rich gastronomic heritage. Gastronomic tourism can serve as a driver of economic growth, reinforce national identity, and revitalize rural regions. It is therefore a strategic sector of the economy, capable of playing an active role in the nation's development.

The article persuasively highlights that Georgia's distinctive cuisine, centuries-old wine culture, and deeply rooted tradition of hospitality provide a solid foundation for the advancement of gastronomic tourism. When marketed effectively, these elements foster a lasting emotional connection with visitors, strengthening Georgia's position as a unique destination.

Gastronomic tourism plays a vital role in Georgia by fostering employment growth, diversifying income sources, and supporting infrastructure development. Ongoing initiatives such as *Wine Road* and *Mziskari* clearly illustrate how gastronomic tourism can help regions address key challenges – particularly in regulating migration processes, strengthening family economies, and preserving cultural traditions. Integrating food culture with tourism not only enhances visitor satisfaction but also promotes a fairer distribution of tourism benefits across regions.

Gastronomic tourism also yields significant cultural benefits for Georgia. It highlights the nation's identity on the international stage, where the role of the toastmaster at the Georgian table – the art of sharing a meal and showcasing distinctive social traditions – sparks interest among travelers seeking authentic experiences. In this way, gastronomy becomes a form of cultural diplomacy, shaping Georgia's image abroad as a hospitable, creative, and historically rich country with a deep cultural heritage. At the same time, this cultural capital must be managed with care to safeguard authenticity against the pressures of commercialization.

The article underscores the absence of a unified national marketing strategy for gastronomic tourism – an issue of critical importance for Georgia. While the Georgian National Tourism Administration has undertaken valuable initiatives and carried out significant marketing activities, the lack of a comprehensive strategy risks weakening the country's brand and underrepresenting its diverse regional cuisines. A national strategy would ensure the consistent and interconnected implementation of marketing efforts, enhance the visibility of regional culinary experiences, and align promotional campaigns with leading international practices. Such a framework should incorporate digital marketing, destination branding, and storytelling that highlights the origins of Georgian dishes, while also embedding gastronomic tourism within legislative and strategic documents. Without this, Georgia risks failing to fully capitalize on one of its most distinctive advantages.

Ultimately, the article concludes that the primary challenge facing Georgia in the development of gastronomic tourism is not a shortage of resources, but the absence of a clearly articulated strategic vision. A unified national marketing strategy would consolidate existing initiatives, strengthen the country's international visibility, and ensure a more comprehensive representation of its gastronomic heritage as a key element of national identity. If such a strategy is thoughtfully designed and effectively implemented, Georgia could establish itself as a prominent destination for gastronomic tourism – where visitors not only enjoy the cuisine but also actively engage in Georgian traditions that embody history, hospitality, and cultural pride.

In this way, gastronomic tourism is steadily evolving into both a driver of economic development and a vehicle of cultural diplomacy, positioning Georgia as a respected and distinctive presence on the global tourism map.

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